

Conceptualization and Significance of Right To Development

Dr Pradeep Kumar Deepak
Assistant Professor
Dept.of History
Govt.Degree College,Amarpur
Gomati, Tripura

Abstract:

This article attempts to clarify the concept of 'Right To Development' in a broader sense. Really, the Right to Development was first recognized in 1981 in article 22 of African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights as a definite individual and collective right. Afterwards, the Right to Development was subsequently proclaimed by the United Nations in 1986 in "Declaration on the Rights to Development", which was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly Resolution 41/128. It is a group right of peoples as opposed to an Individual Right and was reaffirmed by the 1993 'Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action'. If we know the preamble of the declaration on the Rights to Development, "Development is a Comprehensive, economic, social, cultural and political process, which aims at the constant improvement of the well-being of the entire population and individuals on the basis of their active, free and meaningful participation in development and in the fair distribution of benefits resulting there from."

As a matter of fact, Development is a Human Right for All. 21st century is full of new issues and a century of great challenges in which the right to development plays a very pivotal role. The Rio Declaration on Environment and development consisted of 27 principles intended to guide future sustainable development around the world. Some of the principles contained in the Rio declaration may be regarded as 3rd generation rights by European law scholars.

This article specifies the significance of rights to development. UN Millennium declaration on the right to development states, "We, heads of state and government, are committed to making the right to development a reality for every one and to freeing the entire human race from want," in spite of technical advancement, maximum countries are facing the problems of poverty, malnutrition, internal war, environmental degradation, illiteracy etc.. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to acknowledge the significance of right to development by implementing its principles in a practical manner, which is the main theme of my article.

Keywords :- Right, Development, Human rights, Significance, Poverty

Introduction

The 20th century had witnessed unprecedented human losses, devastation and destruction of the two world wars. The human rights discourse and the development discourse emerged simultaneously after the second world war, but there was little in common between the two. The adoption by the United Nations General Assembly of the 'Declaration on the Right to Development in 1986' was the culmination of a long process of re-establishing the unity of human rights. This unity, which existed immediately after the second world war, got split into two categories of rights- civil and political rights (CPRs) on the one hand, and economic, social and cultural rights (ESCRs) on the other. But, the right to development is an overarching composite right, which comprises both CPRs as well as ESCRs. This is established by the fact that RTD (Right to development) is defined as the right to a particular process of development that measures the realization of all human rights- civil, political, economic, social and cultural.

The concept of 'Right to development'(RTD) challenged the artificial division between the two sets of human rights and established the utility as a prerequisite to development. Coined by the Senegalese jurist Keba M'Baye, in 1972, the term has been debated extensively in various international seminars. On 4th December 1986, the United Nations General Assembly formally adopted the Declaration on the Right to Development .

Evolution of the Right To Development:-

The Right to Development(RTD) is one of the most highly debated and contentious issues in International relations. Though the Declaration on the Right to Development was made only in 1986, the origins of the concept of RTD lie much further back in time. Indirect references to the notion were made in various International Human rights instruments in the mid-1940s and early 1950s.^[1]

As early as in 1944, the Philadelphia Declaration of the International Labour Organization affirmed that all human beings had the right to pursue their material well-being and spiritual development. Reference to the content of the concept of 'RTD' was also implicit in various articles of the UN Charter and the International Bill of Rights (ie, UDHR and the 1966 covenants and their protocols). The first explicit references to RTD emerged in the 1970s. The idea was first articulated by the developing countries in the context of 'new International Economic Order' (NIEO), largely understood as a rallying point for eliminating injustice and inequality of nations and peoples. It was only later the eligibility of 'Right to Development' as a 'human right' began to be extensively discussed. Formal recognition of the concept came in 1979 in Resolution 4 (xxxv) of the Commission on Human Rights. The Resolution mandated the United Nations Secretary General to study the conditions required for the effective realization of RTD by all people and individuals.

The right to Development was first recognized in 1981 in article 22 of 'African Charter on Human and People's Rights' as a definite individual and collective right. Article 22(1) provides that "All people shall have the right to their economic, social and cultural development with due regard to their freedom and identity and in the equal enjoyment of the common heritage of mankind".

The various reports and discussions in the Commission and the General Assembly resulted in the formulation of a draft Declaration on the RTD. Finally, the 'Right to Development' was subsequently proclaimed by the United Nations on 4th December 1986 in the "Declaration on the Right to Development", which was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly Resolution 41/128.

The Declaration was adopted by an overwhelming majority, with the United state of America Casting the single dissenting vote. It is a group right of peoples as opposed to an individual right and was reaffirmed by the 1993 Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action. At Vienna, the U.S.A. changed its earlier stance and became a part of the consensus.

In the 1970s and 1980s, it was not uncommon to hear of the right to development as belonging to a 'third generation' of Human rights^[2]. According to this view, the first generation' of Consisted of Civil and Political rights Conceived as liberties against state abuse and economic, social and Cultural rights were regarded as claims against exploiters and oppressors belonging to the second generation. The third generation Consisted of Solidarity right belonging to people and covering global concerns like development, environment, humanitarian assistance, peace, Communication and common heritage.

Whether Conceived as a third generation Human right or not, 'RTD' is based on the premise that Development is itself a human right. In the early 1970s the right to development was publicly posed as a human right ^[3]. and the UN General Assembly proclaimed development as a human right in its 1986 Declaration an the right to development^[4]. The Preamble of the Declaration on the 'RTD' states, "Development is a comprehensive, economic, social, cultural and political process, which aims at the constant improvement of the well-being of the entire population and of all individuals on the basis of their active, free and meaningful participation in development and in the fair distribution of benefits resulting there from"

The Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, also known as Rio Declaration recognize the 'RTD' as one of its 27 principles. 'Rio Declaration' was a short document produced at the 1992 united nations conference on environment and Development (UNCED), informally known as the 'Earth summit'. Some of the principles contained in the Rio Declaration may be regarded as 'Third Generation Right' by European Law scholars. Principles '3' of the declaration states, "The RTD must be fulfilled so as to equitably meet development and environmental needs of present and future generations.

The Vienna Declaration and programme of action states in its article 10, "The world conference on human rights reaffirms the right to Development, as a universal and inalienable right and an integral part of fundamental right. As stated in the Declaration on the Right to development, the human being is the central subject of Development."

While 'Development' facilitates the enjoyment of all human right, the lack of development may not be invoked to justify the abridgement of internationally recognized human rights. States should co-operate with each other in ensuring development and eliminating obstacles to development. The International community should promote an effective International co-operation for the realization of the 'RTD' and eliminates the obstacles to development. Lasting Progress towards the implementation of the 'RTD' requires effective development polices at the national level, as well as equitable economic relations and a favourable economic environment at the International level.

Defining the right to Development:- Article 1, paragraph 1 of the RTD Declaration states, The Right to Development is an inalienable human right by virtue of which every human person and all peoples are entitled to participate in, contribute to, and enjoy economic, social, cultural and political development, in which all human rights and fundamental freedoms can be fully realized.” This Definition establishes ‘RTD’ as a human right, that is inalienable, i.e. it cannot be bargained away. It also establishes the unity of rights by taking of development in which all human rights and fundamental freedoms can be fully realized. It further underscores the entitlement of all persons and peoples to participate in as well as to enjoy the process of development.

Although the word ‘process’ is not mentioned in Article1. Paragraph 1, the definition of development as a process is derivable from the preamble to the ‘RTD’ declaration. The ‘RTD’ approach focuses not only on the ends of development, but also on the means of development. The goals and outcomes of development as the realization of rights are the ends. The process by which such goals are actually achieved, in a progressive manner, consists also of the ‘means’ of programmes and policies and instrumental changes needed for realizing the rights. The principles of equity, non-discrimination, transparency, accountability and participation provide the defining parameters of a rights based process of development^[5].

To have a ‘Right’ means to have a claim to something of value on other people, institution, the state or the International community, which in turn have the obligation of providing or helping to provide something of values. Professor Amartya sen has described the essential characteristics of ‘Right’ as follows, “rights are entitlements that require co-related duties. If person a has a right to some X, then there has to be some agency, say B, that has a duty to promote A with X, (Sen 2000, P-228). Prof. Sen describes the matching of rights with duties in terms of the Kantian concept of perfect and Imperfect obligations.

Everyone having a right to food does not mean much unless agent-specific duties and methods of fulfilling the obligation of the duty-holders can be identified. When such duties can be specified precisely for particular agents responsible for the realization of that right, it is subjected to perfect obligations, i.e. amenable to legal enforcement. This view of right evolved over time to what seen describes as the Kantian view of Imperfect obligations, wherein claims are addressed generally to anyone who can help, and the right become norms of behavior or action of the agents-individuals, the state or the International community- who can contribute to the fulfillment of these rights.

According to I.E. “RTD is the right to a process of development where all human rights-CPRs (civil and political rights) and ESCRs (Economic, social and cultural rights) are realized. The outcome of a process of development is in itself a human right, which entails obligations. The process is a programme a plan executed over time maintaining consistency and sustainability, with phased realization of the outcome.”^[6] (Report of the Independent Expert Dr. Arjun Sengupta to the Human rights commission)

Perhaps the most frequent linking of human right and human development in policy has been the 80-called ‘right-based’ approach to development. The ‘right way to development’ is the shorthand expression for the ‘human rights approach to development assistance, as articulated by Andre Frankvits of the Human Rights council of Australia. UNDP states, “Human devalopmeny shares a common vision with human rights. The goal is human freedom. And in pursuing capabilities and realizing rights, this freedom is vital. People must be free to exercise their choice and to partipicle in decision-making that affect their lives. Human development and human rights are mutually reinforcing, helping to secure the well-being and dignity of all people, building self-respect and the respect and the respect of others.”^[7]

As per 'article 2' of the Declaration on the right to development, "The human person is the central subject of development and should be the active participant and beneficiary of the right to development. All human beings have a responsibility for development, individually and collectively, taking into account the need for full respect for their human right and fundamental freedoms as well as their duties to the community, which alone can ensure the free and complete fulfillment of the human beings and they should therefore promote and protect and appropriate political, social and economic order for development." (Adopted by general Assembly Resolution 41/128 of 4th December 1986)

Significance Of Right To Development In Indian Perspective:-

India is one of the greatest and oldest champions of the International community's struggle for preservation, protection and promotion of human rights. The Rigveda, which is considered to be the oldest document of human civilization, declares that all human beings are equal and they are all brothers. The Atharvaveda, likewise, proclaims that all human beings have equal right over food and water. In our religious text, it is written, "sarve bhawantu sukhinah, sarve santu Niramahas. That is, let all people be happy. In fact, protection and promotion of human rights are possible only in a society where all people, irrespective of their castes, creeds, sex and religions, live happily and only then in real sense, the significance of Right to development can be realized.

While the state is the primary duty holder, the RTD Declaration puts the responsibility for ensuring development on everyone – individuals, national governments and the International community. "All human beings have a responsibility for development, individually and collectively," states Article 4 of the declaration. But, states have the primary duty to create national and International conditions favourable for the realization of the right.

As a matter of fact, Development is a human right for all. 21st century is full of new issues and it is a century of great challenges in which the 'RTD' plays a very pivotal role. Recognizing a right as a human right raises the status of that right to one with universal applicability and articulates a norm of action for the people. The institutions, the state and the international community, as well as the other agencies of society including individuals, to implement that right. Considering that under the provisions of the universal Declaration of Human rights everyone is entitled to a social and International order in which the rights and freedoms set forth in that declaration can be fully realized. Considering that the elimination of the massive and flagrant violation of the human rights of the peoples and individuals affected by situations such as those resulting from colonialism, neo-colonialism, apartheid, all forms of racism and racial discrimination, foreign domination occupation, aggression and threats against national sovereignty, national unity and territorial integrity and threats of war would contribute in the in the establishment of circumstances propitious to the development of a great part of mankind.

India's independence represented for its people the start of an epoch that was imbued with a new vision. In 1947, the country commenced its long march to overcome the colonial legacy of economic development, gross poverty, near total illiteracy, wide prevalence of diseases and stark social inequality and injustice. 1947 was only the first stop, the first break – the end of colonial political control; centuries of backwardness were now to be overcome, the promises of freedom struggle to be fulfilled and people's hope to be met. On being sworn as the first Prime minister of the country, Pandit J.L.Nehru called for "the ending of poverty, ignorance, disease and inequality of opportunity." Mahatma Gandhi had always insisted that India would become truly independent only when the poorest of its people would be free from sufferings. The Bhagwat Puran is much more emphatic on the basis of principles of socialism an equitable sharing of the blessing of God- where Narada tells Yudhisthira, "One is entitled to take as much as is sufficient for fulfilling up the stomach, he who takes more than this is guilty of the theft and deserves to be punished."^[8] Srimad Bhagwadgita also proclaims, "we may not own anything beyond our strict requirements, but should share equally with all God's creatures the means of subsistence."^[9]

The rights of food, primary health care and primary education are the three rights that have been identified by the independent expert (IE) for immediate action as a part of the process of the realization of the Right to Development (RTD)^[10] The focus on these have precedence over other rights. All rights are equally important and different countries may choose to implement other right to which they attach priority. Particularly in a developing country like India the right to food, education and healthcare are important, because they are complementary to the non-derogable right to life, which is the foundation of all rights. Many other rights, such as the right to shelter, livelihood, information, association, representation, etc. are equally critical to the process of development.

1) Right to Food:- Although there is no explicit provision for the right to food in the constitution of India, comparable human right related provisions are enshrined in the fundamental Rights as well as the Directive Principles of state policy. Article 21 of the constitution, which ensures a fundamental right to life and personal liberty, is seen as the fulcrum of the justiciability of the right to food.^[11] In India, it is estimated that 350-400 million are below the poverty line, 75% of them in the rural areas. But, there have been some encouraging developments in India regarding the enforcement of the right to food, with courts taking up the public interest litigation (PIL) cases relating to the violation of the right. By far the most significant case relating to the right to food is that of PUCL v. Union of India and others.^[12] The PIL petition, seeking enforcement of the right to food, was filed by the People's Union for Civil Liberties (PUCIL) in the Supreme Court on 9 May 2001 against the Union of India, FCI (Food Corporation of India) and the state governments of Orissa, Rajasthan, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh and Maharashtra. Prompted by reports of acute starvation in various parts of the country, the petition draws attention to the fact that in spite of 50 million tonnes of foodgrains lying in FCI storehouses, 208 million Indians are affected by chronic hunger. Among the questions the petition raised were the following:-

- 1) Does not the right to life under Article 21 of the constitution of India include the right to food?
- 2) Does not the right to food imply that the state has a duty to provide food, especially in situations of drought, to people who have been affected and are not in position to purchase food?

Expressing serious concern over the increasing number of starvation deaths and food insecurity despite overflowing government storehouses, the Supreme Court broadened the scope of petition from the six states to include the entire country. It accepted the importance of actions like free distribution of foodgrains to the poor, but emphasized the need for long-term solutions aimed at raising the capabilities of the people by various means, including providing employment. In its orders of 23rd July 2001, the Supreme Court held, "what is of utmost importance is to see that food is provided to the aged, infirm, disabled, destitute, women, destitute men, who are in danger of starvation, pregnant and lactating women and destitute children, especially in cases, where they or members of their family do not have sufficient funds to provide food for them." Moreover, the court directed the states to see that all the PDS (public Distribution system) shops, if closed, are re-opened and start functioning within one week from the day of the Order and that regular supplies are made available.

On 28th November 2001, the Supreme Court came out with a significant 'Interim Order' directing the state Government to implement fully eight different centrally-sponsored schemes on food security. These are:-

- (i) National Old Age Pension Scheme (NOAPS)
- (ii) National Family Benefit Scheme (NFBS)
- (iii) National Monetary Benefit Scheme (NMBS)

- (iv) National Programme for Nutritional support to Primary Education or the Mid-Day Meals Scheme.
- (v) Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS)
- (vi) Antyodaya Child Development Services (ICDS)
- (vii) Antyodaya Anna Yojana (AAY)
- (viii) Targeted Public Distribution system (TPDS)
- (ix) Annapoorna scheme.

(2) Right to Education :- The right to Development is meaningless without having the right to education particularly for our country, where the literacy rate in the country is only 65.38%. I think that one of the main causes of poverty is illiteracy. The importance of education has been recognized in Indian policy making from the very beginning. Article 45 of the constitution of India stipulated that the state would endeavour to provide, within 10 years, free and compulsory education for all children below 14 years of age. This provision was, however, contained in the section on Direction Principles of state policy. But, a landmark development in the field of elementary education was the observation that came in the course of a judgment in Unni Krishnan, J.P.V. state of Andhra Pradesh in 1993. This judgment lent strength to the growing demand for a 'right to education', which culminated in the 93rd constitutional Amendment in 2001. As per this amendment, education has been granted the status of a fundamental right, with a constitutional guarantee that the state shall provide free and compulsory education to all children in the age group of 6-14 years.

The elementary education system in India is the second largest in the world with 149.4 million children in the 6-14 years age group and 2.9 million teachers.^[13] The major thrust of education policy at the primary level is on improving enrolment, retention and achievement of children of the relevant age group and reducing disparities among different segments of the population. A number of schemes have been initiated by the centre in the field of primary education since the National policy on education was announced. Some of these are as follows:-

- (i) District Primary Education Programme (DPEP)
- (ii) Operation Black Board
- (iii) Mahila Samakhya
- (iv) Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan
- (v) Education Guarantee Scheme and Alternative and Innovation Education.
- (vi) Mid-day Meals Scheme
- (vii) Teacher Education

(viii) Lok Jumbish

(ix) Shiksha Karmi Project and

(x) Janshala

Despite the progress made in the field of education, India has still not achieved the goal of Universalisation of education, though enrolment rates have been increased. The Secondary education sector has also witnessed significant growth since independence. Recent initiatives for qualitative improvement in Secondary education have focused on vocationalisation of education, improvement of science education, computer literacy and providing boarding facilities for girls. But, at present, only 4.8% students, passing out of the secondary school level opt for the vocational stream at the 10+2 stage, against a target of 25% and still a lot of progress in this field is required.

(3.) Right to health :-

The widely accepted definition of health as a 'state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing' underscores the invisibility and interdependence of rights as they relate to health. Especially in Indian context, the constitution of India deals with the subject of health in substantive manner under the Directive Principles of State Policy' through which it mandates the state to take measures to improve the conditions of health care for the people – 'Article 39' imposes an obligation upon the state to direct its policy towards ensuring that the health and strength of people are not abused. Similarly, 'Article 47' enjoins the state to raise the level of nutrition and standard of living of its people and improve public health. There has been a steady improvement in life expectancy at birth, which rose from 49 years in 1970 to 63 years in 1998.

The foundation of India's health policy was laid by the Bhore commission Report in 1946. The Report established primary health care as the foundation for the national health care system, and developed the first patterns for primary health care facilities and health personnel in the public sector. The Bhore commission enunciated the principle that primary health care is a basic right to which people should not be denied access because of their inability to pay or for other Socio – economic reasons. Building on this thinking over the years, India became a strong supporter of the 'Alma-Ata declaration of 1978,' where it committed itself to attain the goal of 'Health for All' based on a primary health care approach.

The first National Health Policy (NHP) was approved by the Indian Parliament in 1983. In Indian sub-continent, Health is a subject in the concurrent list of the Indian Constitution, which means that the responsibility is shared by the Central, State and local Governments. Still, the health-care in India particularly in rural side is pathetic. It requires utmost care and incentives from the Government side in a practical manner. The poor people having meager income fall prey to fatal diseases due to their improper diets. They must be cared, only then we can see the 'right to development,' in a true sense in Indian perspective because as per 'Article 6' of the right to development, "States should take steps to eliminate obstacles to development resulting from failure to observe civil and political rights, as well as

economic, social and cultural rights.’ (General Assembly Resolution 41/128 of 4 December 1986, Article 6 para-3.)

Problem in Implementing the Right to Development.

As a matter of fact, Development has to be judged from the point of view of actual implementation and not merely on the basis of plans. Non-implementation may be manifested in –

- i) Leakages of food-grains meant for public distribution to the open-market.
- ii) Offering of private tuitions by teachers and
- iii) Running of Private clinics and medical facilities by doctors.

We have to move from identifying the problems and examining the formal commitment to human rights in assessing the implementation and efficacy in practice. The problems encountered in implementing the ‘rights to Development’ (RID) includes

- i) Resource constraints
- ii) Problems of governance and lack of political will
- iii) Lack of an overall framework for Implementation
- iv) Lack of appropriate indicators and bench-marks for monitoring.
- v) Disparity in nature of challenges across areas and circumstances such as :- regional disparity, rural-urban disparity, gender disparity & class disparity etc.

Required Remedies in Implementation of right to Development :-

If we want to implement the ‘RTD’, then we must think the poorest of the poor people of our society. Because the real India lives in villages, where still the right to food, education and health care are mere a story, far from the realities. As per my views are concerned, in India, accountability is conspicuous by its absence – even where people can be identified or pinpointed for lack of implementation, no steps are taken against them and punishment is rare. Above –all, it is essential to keep in mind and to highlight the interdependence of all the rights in the context of ‘RTD’. For actual implementation of ‘RTD’ these approach may be useful in Indian perspective:-

Vector Approach:- The concept of RTD goes beyond mere growth in income or consumption standards. It is a ‘vector’ consisting of a largenumber of elements. Each element of the vector is a human right just as the vector itself is a human right. All the elements are interdependent, both at any point in time and over a period of time. For example, realizing the right to health will depend on the level of realization of other righs such as the right to food, to housing etc. RTD will be realized if all the

elements of the vector improve while any one of the others deteriorates, it will not be possible to claim any net improvement in RTD.^[14]

Step-by-step Approach and significance of RTD:-

The realization of RTD has to process step by step, in tandem with the changing world economy and the strength of the human rights movement. Since all rights and corresponding freedoms cannot be realized immediately and simultaneously, it might be useful to concentrate initially on a few areas that may be regarded as basic to all other rights. These are the rights to food, health care and education.^[15] It is not that other rights are not important, but these rights cater to the most basic needs of the people and facilitate the realization of other rights. These may also be taken as the minimum indicators of RTD that have to be satisfied and that would claim priority in the use of the states' financial and administrative resources.

As we know the India is a developing country. So, right to Development is of utmost importance for our country and if we introspect the fact we can say that poverty is the most object violation of human rights, denying as it does practically all the freedoms to the people affected. The eradication of poverty would, therefore, be a first step towards the 'progressive realization' of the human right to development.

While the state is the primary duty holder, the RTD declaration puts the responsibility for ensuring development on everyone individuals, national government and the International Community. As per Article 4 of the declaration, "All human beings have a responsibility for development, individually and collectively." But, states have the primary duty to create national and International conditions favourable for the realization of the right. UN Millennium Declaration on the 'RTD' states, "we, heads of state and Government, are committed to making the right to Development a reality for everyone and to freeing the entire human race from want."

Conclusion :- In spite of technical excellence maximum countries of the world and maximum states of our country are facing the problems of poverty, malnutrition, internal conflicts, environmental degradation, illiteracy etc. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to acknowledge the significance of the Right to development by implementing its principle in a practical manner. The right to food, primary health care and primary education are the three rights that have been identified by the independent Expert(I.E) for immediate action as a part of the process of the realization of the right to the process of the realization of the Right to development(RTD).

Particularly for a developing country like India, it is very much imperative to eradicate the constraints in implementing the right to development at grass-root levels. The poorest of the poor people of our society must be taken care and the disparity in nature such as regional disparity, rural-urban disparity, gender disparity and class disparity should be removed, only then the fruits of 'right to development (RTD) can be utilized for the betterment of human beings. If the 'right to development'(RTD) is truly implemented, a day will come when India will definitely become a developed country of the world.

References :-

1. Sayers Larissa, Chatterjee Rajib and Rawat Santosh, 2004, *The Right To Development*, Sage Publication India Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi, Page -45.
2. Marks, Stephen P, 1981, Emerging Human Rights : A New Generation for the 1980's, Rutgers Law Review, Vol-33, No-2, PP-435-452.
3. Judge M'Baye Keba, 1972, Lecture at the International Institute of Human Rights, Human Rights journal, Vol-5, No – 2-3, PP-505-534
4. UNO, General Assembly Resolution 41/128, 4th December 1986, Declaration of the Right to Development.
5. Sayers Larissa, Chatterjee Rajib and Rawat Santosh, 2004, *The Right to Development*, Sage Publication India Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi; Page -51.
6. Ibid, PP-51.
7. UNDP, Human Development Report, 2001, P-9.
8. Bhagvat Puran, chapter 14, Verse – 8
9. Srimad Bhagvad Gita, chapter – 3, verse – 12
10. Sengupta, Dr Arjun, (Independent Expert), 7-8 April 2002 & 19-22 October 2002, Workshop on A project to Development, New Delhi
11. PUCL v. Union of India (sec 196 of 2001), Petition filed by PUCL (a voluntary organization fighting for civil liberties) against the Union of India.
12. Ibid
13. 'National Policy on Education', New Delhi : Dept of Education, GOI. [http ;// www. Education.nic.in / html web / natpol.htm](http://www.Education.nic.in/htmlweb/natpol.htm).
14. Sengupta, Dr.Arjun, (Independent expert), 17 August 2006, 'Second Report to the Human Rights Commission, A/55/306 New Delhi.
15. Sayers Larissa, Chatterjee Rajib and Rawat Santosh, 2004, *The Right To Development*, Sage Publication India Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi, P-55.